
**METHODOLOGICAL GAPS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
MEASUREMENT SCALES FOR AI-ENABLED VIRTUAL LEARNING
ENVIRONMENTS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13770510

Ana Luize Correa Bertoncini¹

¹Doutorado em Administração – Universidade do Estado de Santa Catarina

E-mail: analuizec@gmail.com

Lattes: <http://lattes.cnpq.br/8116359113043883>

Eduardo Henrique de Borba¹

¹Doutorado em Administração – Universidade do Estado de Santa Catarina

E-mail: ehenrique@uoc.edu

Lattes: <http://lattes.cnpq.br/4307482867867640>

ABSTRACT: Artificial Intelligence (AI) has profoundly transformed Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs), positioning them as pivotal in online education. This study conducts a systematic review of literature from Web of Science, Science Direct, Springer Link, Emerald Insight, and EBSCO Host to assess the application of measurement scales in AI-enhanced VLEs. The review identifies high-impact articles published in leading journals, yet it also reveals a notable deficiency in robust measurement scales. Many reviewed studies lack methodological rigor in key stages of scale development. Essential constructs related to student perceptions and motivational factors influencing VLE use are highlighted, emphasizing the need for more comprehensive and reliable scales. Effective measurement tools are crucial for accurately evaluating the performance and impact of AI-powered VLEs. The study advocates for the development of rigorous, well-defined scales to ensure precise assessments and improvements in online learning environments. Addressing these gaps will enhance the effectiveness and quality of AI-integrated educational platforms.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Virtual Learning Environment; Measurement Scale; Systematic Review.

1. INTRODUCTION

Technology has decisively transformed teaching and learning practices, with tools such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data, learning analytics, and cloud computing being adopted to varying degrees. These advances have resulted in new learning environments such as e-learning, m-learning, tele-education, and Virtual Learning Environments (VLE). The growing academic interest in exploring how these technological innovations can enrich traditional teaching and address the challenges of their implementation is well-documented (Cheung et al., 2021).

Technology is now integral to students' daily lives (Roblek et al., 2018), providing access to unprecedented information (Mondigo & Lao, 2017). AI, in turn, offers the necessary versatility (Vodenko & Lyausheva, 2020), introducing collaborative tools, artificial neural networks, and autonomous systems (Jalal & Mahmood, 2019) that adapt to the contemporary demands of virtual teaching.

The need to adopt virtual learning environments has become increasingly evident in recent years. The shift to virtual learning, driven by several factors, has highlighted the importance of integrating advanced technologies to enhance the educational experience. This shift has highlighted the need to overcome challenges associated with engagement and learning effectiveness on digital platforms, reflecting a growing recognition of the importance of VLEs in modern education (Hew et al., 2020).

In online learning, motivation is influenced differently than in traditional models, with system expectations, technology adoption, and usability playing critical roles in satisfaction and intention to use (Khan et al., 2024; Panigrahi et al., 2021). AI has become an indispensable resource for enhancing systems and simulating human tutoring capabilities, which increases integration and engagement (Yuce et al., 2019).

Recent studies emphasize the critical role of quality assessment practices for VLEs, highlighting their impact on motivation and learning. Effective use of appropriate measurement scales is essential for evaluating and enhancing these virtual environments (Panigrahi et al., 2021). This article evaluates how academic literature addresses the development of measurement scales for AI-enabled VLEs. It includes a systematic literature review focusing on the adoption antecedents of these environments and an analysis of the measurement scales. The review incorporates bibliometric analysis, a narrative assessment of selected articles, and a theoretical framework to provide a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

To define relevant keywords for our search, we will concentrate on the evolution of Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs) and the transformative impact of AI-driven platforms on online teaching. The focus will also be on the necessity of employing rigorous measurement scales to evaluate and enhance VLE quality and usability, ensuring they meet user expectations.

The increasing adoption of VLEs addresses the limitations of traditional education and the demand for modern solutions. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become pivotal, introducing intelligent tutoring systems that simulate empathy and enhance student interactions and learning

experiences (Arguedas et al., 2016; Yuce et al., 2019). These advancements lead to more personalized learning environments, which boost motivation and academic performance. Effective e-learning is influenced by interactive design and structural characteristics, including usability and information system quality, which are crucial for user satisfaction and learning effectiveness (Maldonado et al., 2009; Kumar & Tandon, 2024; Yuce et al., 2019).

Evaluating VLEs and their effective use is essential to ensure these digital systems fulfill educational needs and provide an optimal learning experience. Morales-Salas, Infante-Moro, and Gallardo-Pérez (2020) underscore that detailed measurement scales are vital for analyzing usability, pedagogical effectiveness, and user satisfaction. These metrics identify strengths and areas for improvement, allowing for targeted enhancements in VLE functionality. Furthermore, Arguedas et al. (2016) emphasize the importance of addressing both technical aspects and users' subjective needs, including social interaction and personalized learning. Regular evaluations using these scales ensure VLEs remain dynamic and responsive to evolving educational demands. The application of measurement scales is integral to refining VLEs, offering insights into usability, system quality, and user satisfaction, thus driving continuous improvement (Ghai & Tandon, 2023; Khan et al., 2024; Kumar & Tandon, 2024).

3. METHODOLOGY

To achieve the research objective of evaluating measurement scales for AI-driven Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs), a systematic search of international databases was conducted. This analysis builds on the research by Bertoncini, Serafim, and Borba (2023). The search initially used broad terms such as “e-learning” and “virtual learning environment” along with “motivation,” “engagement,” or “student motivation.” After refining, the key descriptors identified were “artificial intelligence,” “virtual learning environment,” and “student motivation” due to their relevance.

The bibliographic survey was performed using Web of Science, Science Direct, Springer Link, Emerald Insight, and EBSCO Host, chosen for their significance in Social Sciences. Inclusion criteria were articles in English, published in journals or conferences, featuring scales or measures related to the study's focus, with no time restrictions, and search terms appearing in any section of the articles.

No prior systematic reviews on scales for evaluating VLEs were identified. To synthesize the literature and guide future research, we followed the PRISMA 2020 guidelines

(Page et al., 2021), as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 – Procedures for systematic article searches.

Steps		n
Database	Web of Science	1
	Science Direct	25
	Springer Link	40
	Emerald Insight	19
	EBSCO Host	30
	Total	115
Filter	Not duplicated	87
	Selected after reading the titles, abstracts, and keywords	29
	Final sample after complete reading	15

Note: n (number of articles).

Source: The authors.

In August 2024, a systematic search identified 115 articles. After removing duplicates and excluding non-research papers, 87 articles were reviewed, resulting in 29 relevant papers. Ultimately, 15 articles focused on measuring perceptions of Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs). Articles not related to VLEs, or lacking measurement scales were excluded. Data management used Mendeley, and bibliometric tools (VOSviewer, Gephi, Research Rabbit) showed no significant relationships, leading to analysis via Excel based on Donthu et al. (2021). The narrative review briefly described the dimensions and results, highlighting the chosen scales and their alignment with AI in VLEs. The analysis followed DeVellis's (2017) guidelines, outlining eight essential steps for creating valid and reliable scales.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A systematic review combines research findings using predefined criteria for meta-analysis. While effective in health research, it faces challenges in social sciences due to study variability. This study reviews 15 articles with diverse data, presenting a quantitative overview followed by an evaluation of measurement scale validity and reliability.

4.1 Bibliometric Results

Bibliographic methodology applies mathematical and statistical research to examine patterns in document publication and usage (Ramos-Rodríguez & Ruíz-Navarro, 2004). It is a quantitative approach to analyzing bibliographic data. Conducting bibliometric analysis serves multiple purposes, including identifying new trends in article and journal performance, collaboration patterns, and research constituencies, as well as investigating the intellectual structure of a particular field in contemporary literature (Donthu et al., 2021).

For this review, we conducted a performance analysis to assess research component contributions to a field. Descriptive analysis is the signature feature of bibliometric investigations, and it is more analytical than empirical research's participant background or profile presentation (Donthu et al., 2021). We evaluated publication-related performance (authors, countries, year of publication, and journals) and citation metrics. Table 2 displays the publication-related metrics:

Table 2 – Performance analysis - publication-related metrics

Publication-related metrics	
Total publications (TP)	15
Number of contributing authors (NCA)	47
Sole-author publications (AS)	0
Co-authored publications (CA)	15
Number of active years of publication (NAY)	8
Productivity per active year of publication (PAY) [TP / NAY]	1,875

Source: Primary data, 2024.

We analyzed 15 articles authored by 47 different researchers, with Urvashi Tandon being the only co-author of multiple papers (Ghai & Tandon, 2023; Kumar & Tandon, 2024). The sample includes no sole-author publications, with each article having 2 to 6 authors. The first authors were from various countries: India, Jordan, Malaysia, Mexico, Morocco, Pakistan, South Korea, Turkey, the UK, and Zimbabwe. This diversity and the lack of co-author networks, as seen in software analyses like Gephi and Research Rabbit, contribute to the observed fragmentation. The articles were published over 8 years, from 2009 to the present, with an average productivity of 1.875 papers per active year. Detailed metrics are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Dashboard of publication-related metrics regarding year and authors

Source: Primary data, 2024.

The number of authors per article may indicate that interdisciplinary teams are necessary to integrate education with technical issues. Regarding the countries, the authors are mostly affiliated with institutions in Eastern countries. Although China passed the EUA in publications productivity in 2020 (Owens, 2024), this noteworthy point contrasts with the fact that scientific publications are still concentrated in Western countries, mainly North America and Europe. The 47 authors are from 15 different countries, with the largest concentration (14) in India, which could imply that this country is a hub in the subject and/or is ensuring the frontline. This conclusion is supported by the systematic review of Djeki et al. (2022), which reveals that India ranks seventh out of 151 nations in terms of publishing the highest number of papers on e-learning.

The final publication-related metric assessed was the journal type. Out of 15 articles, 14 were published in journals, and one was presented at a conference. Notably, the journal “Education and Information Technologies” had seven publications, focusing on the intersection of information and communication technology with education (see Table 3).

Table 3 – Performance analysis - Number of publications per journal/conference (NPJ)

Reference	Journal	NPJ
Al-Adwan et al. (2023); Ghai and Tandon (2023); Khan et al. (2024); Kumar and Tandon (2024); Patil and Undale (2023); Vanitha and Alathur (2021); Zhou et al. (2022)	Education and Information Technologies	7
Alami and El Idrissi (2022)	Arab Gulf Journal of Scientific Research	1
Panigrahi et al. (2021)	Information Technology and People	1
Salam and Farooq (2020)	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education	1
Li and Yu (2020)	Journal of Data, Information and Management	1
Yuce et al. (2019)	Online Information Review	1
Cabada et al. (2017)	Telematics and Informatics	1
Kashive et al. (2021)	The International Journal of Information and Learning Technology	1
Reference	Conference	NPJ
Maldonado et a. (2009)	ICCIT 2009 - 4th International Conference on Computer Sciences and Convergence Information Technology	1

Source: Primary data, 2024.

Another type of metric for performance analysis is related to citations. While publishing indicates productivity, citation quantifies the impact and influence (Donthu et al., 2021). Table 4 displays the citation-related metrics:

Table 4 – Performance analysis - Citation-related metrics

Citation-related metrics	
Total citations (TC)	948
Average citations (AC)	
Per publication	63,2
Per active year	118,5
Per total period	63,2

Source: Primary data, 2024.

The sample articles collectively received 948 citations, averaging 63.2 citations per publication and 118.5 citations per active year. Since the first article's publication in 2009, the average citation rate has been 63.2 per period. Five articles received over 100 citations each: Al-Adwan et al. (2023) [198], Salam and Farooq (2020) [147], Kashive et al. (2021) [114], Cabada et al. (2017) [110], and Panigrahi et al. (2021) [102]. Two articles had 50 to 99 citations: Maldonado et al. (2009) [63] and Yuce et al. (2019) [61]. Six articles received between 10 and 49 citations, while three had fewer than 10 citations.

Citation counts can vary based on several factors, including the foundational nature of the research, the age of the publication, and field-specific citation norms (Van Noorden et al., 2014; Waltman, 2016). High citation counts may indicate the utility and influence of the scales developed in these articles. However, a more detailed analysis, such as science mapping, is needed to fully understand these citation trends (Donthu et al., 2021).

Finally, we related publication and citation metrics to give a better overview, as exposed in Table 5:

Table 5 – Performance analysis - Citation-and-publication-related metrics

Citation-and-publication-related metrics	
Collaboration index (CI) $[(NCA / TP) / TP]$	8,99
Collaboration coefficient (CC) $[1-(TP/NCA)]$	0,68
Number of cited publications (NCP)	15,00
Proportion of cited publications (PCP)	100,00%
Citations per cited publication (CCP)	63,20

Source: Primary data, 2024.

While the collaboration index (CI) measures the extent of collaboration among the research constituents, the collaboration coefficient (CC) standardizes the extent of author collaboration between 0 and 1 (Donthu et al., 2021); in other words, it relates the number of contributing authors to the total publication. In this sample, CI is 8,99 and CC 0,68, indicating an above-average collaboration among authors. As for the citation-related metrics, all papers were cited (100%), averaging 63.2 citations per article. These relationships corroborate the analyses developed above regarding large, probably multidisciplinary teams necessary for the development of a scale and a likely high impact of the publications.

4.2 Narrative Review

A narrative review explores research progress over time or across traditions, integrating various perspectives through metanarratives. It emphasizes transparency and a clear strategy for evaluating conclusions. This study used thematic analysis to review measurement scales, following DeVellis's (2017) 8 key processes for ensuring validity and reliability. Before analyzing the scales, we summarized the key dimensions and precedents (see Table 6).

Table 6 – Dimensions and results obtained in the sample articles

Reference	Dimension of Interest	Precedent Dimensions Evaluated	Results
Al-Adwan et al. (2023)	Behavior Intention to Use metaverse-based learning platforms	Personal Innovativeness In IT, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Enjoyment, Self-Efficacy, Perceived Cyber Risks; and Perceived Ease of Use.	Perceived usefulness, personal innovativeness in IT, and perceived enjoyment are key enablers of students' behavioral intentions to adopt the metaverse. Perceived cyber risk is the primary inhibitor of students' metaverse adoption intentions.
Alami and El Idrissi (2022)	E-learning Continuance Usage	Social Influence; Perceived Ease of Use; Perceived Usefulness, Confirmation, and Satisfaction.	E-learning acceptance depends significantly on the students' satisfaction, perceived ease of use, and perceived usefulness.
Cabada et al. (2017)	Intention to Use e-learning software	Perceived Usefulness; Perceived Ease of Use; Perceived Satisfaction; and Attitude in Favor of Use	Perceived satisfaction positively impacted Intention to Use, and students who used the software achieved more significant

			learning gains than those who learned using the traditional method.
Ghai and Tandon (2023)	Usability of e-learning	Instructional Design, Gamification Motivation, Game Elements, Game Dynamics, and Game Mechanics.	Gamification is a multi-dimensional construct significantly predicted by elements, game dynamics, motivation, and game mechanics in e-learning.
Kashive et al. (2021)	Intention to Use AI-enabled e-learning	Personal Learning Network; Personal Learning Profile; Personal Learning Usefulness, Attitude, and Satisfaction. Effectiveness; Perceived Environment; Perceived Ease of Use; Perceived	Satisfaction mediates between perceived ease of use and intention. The Personal Learning profile has come out to significantly impact perceived effectiveness. The multigroup analysis also showed that attitude and satisfaction level affected the intention to use the e-learning
Khan et al. (2024)	E-learning system	ICT adoption; Social IoT; Artificial Intelligence; Digital Literacy; Pedagogical Digital Competence; and Technostress	Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and the Internet of Things (IoT) significantly impact e-learning systems. Artificial Intelligence contributes only partially.
Kumar and Tandon (2024)	Behavior Intention to Use E-learning	Security; Power; Achievement; Hedonism; Conformity; and Digital Technology Awareness	Security, Power, Achievement, and Hedonism have a significant positive impact on the behavioral intention to use e-learning.
Li and Yu (2020)	Intention to Continue Using E-learning	Previous Experience; IT Competence; Self-Efficacy; Perceived Ease of Use; Perceived Usefulness; Affect; and Attitude.	Students' intention to return to the e-learning environment is highly associated with their attitude and affection toward the e-learning tool.
Maldonado et al. (2009)	E-learning Usage Behavior	Social Influence, Facilitating Conditions, and Motivation	Student motivation has a positive influence on e-learning adoption.
Panigrahi et al. (2021)	Perceived Learning Effectiveness in E-learning	Internet Self-Efficacy, Information Quality; System Quality, Service Quality; Behavioral Engagement, Emotional Engagement; and Cognitive Engagement	Behavioral, Emotional, and Cognitive Engagements positively impact the Perceived Effectiveness of learning. A positive relationship exists between the Quality of the Information System and Engagement in e-learning.
Patil and Undale (2023)	Intention to Continue Using e-learning	Performance expectancy; Intention to continue use; Effort expectancy; Availability of Resources, and Self-efficacy.	Performance expectancy and availability of resources are significant indicators of intention to continue using e-learning.
Salam and Farooq (2020)	Net Benefits of Web-Based Collaborative Learning Information System (WBCLIS)	System Quality, Information Quality; Service Quality, Quality of Sociability, System Usage; and User Satisfaction	The Quality of Sociability positively impacts System Usage and User Satisfaction, and these last two dimensions strongly predict the Net Benefits of WBCLIS.
Vanitha and Alathur (2021)	E-learning adoption	System Quality, Information Quality, Service Quality, Collaborative Quality, Computer Skill, Internet Self-efficacy, Learner Attitude, Learner Behavior, Learner Confidence, Prior Knowledge, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Satisfaction, and Learner Characteristics.	Technology and learner dimension factors significantly influence e-learning adoption.
Yuce et al. (2019)	Learning Performance in Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS)	Knowledge Quality, System Quality, Service Quality, Task-Technology Fit, Satisfaction, and Motivation.	The Quality of Knowledge, System, and Service positively impacts Satisfaction and improves Task-Technology Fit—and student Satisfaction with ITS increases their Motivation.
Zhou et al. (2022)	Behavior Intention to Use Virtual Learning	Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, Social Influence, and Facilitating Conditions	Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, and Social Influence were confirmed to be positive predictors of Behavioral Intention to use virtual learning.

Source: The authors.

The selected articles investigated several dimensions of Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs), including technology adoption, information system efficiency, users' intention to use technology, perceived effectiveness of online learning, and system usability. These dimensions reflect how users integrate digital tools, assess VLE performance, and interact with these platforms. All analyzed articles validated their hypotheses using robust statistical methods, providing valuable insights into VLE effectiveness across these dimensions.

Regarding measurement scales, many studies utilized the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis (1989) to evaluate usability and acceptance, such as those by Kumar and Tandon (2024), Alami and El Idrissi (2022), and Cabada et al. (2017). This model, known for its predictive accuracy, was also employed by Li and Yu (2020) with added emotional and experiential variables. Other studies expanded the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model by Venkatesh et al. (2003), incorporating new dimensions to better address technology acceptance, as seen in research by Khan et al. (2024), Patil and Undale (2023), and Maldonado et al. (2009). Panigrahi et al. (2021) applied Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) and the DeLone and McLean (1992) model to assess system quality, while Salam and Farooq (2020) updated DeLone and McLean's framework to include sociability aspects. Yuce et al. (2019) evaluated intelligent tutoring systems using scales based on Chiu et al. (2007), which integrate justice theory into information system success. The diversity of approaches and models used underscores the complexity of evaluating VLEs and highlights the need for context-specific assessment tools.

A comparative analysis of the development of the measurement scales used in the articles that comprise the research sample is presented individually in Table 7. Based on the postulates outlined by DeVellis (2017), the assessment consists of eight stages:

- 1. Clarity in the Definition of the Measure:** Clearly define the concept the scale intends to measure, ensuring that the measure is specific and well-defined.
- 2. Generation of the Item Set:** Develop and describe an initial set of items that adequately represent the concept to be assessed.
- 3. Selection of the Appropriate Measurement Format:** Select the appropriate format for the scale items in addition to the ideal statistical evaluation model.
- 4. Expert Review of the Items:** Submit the scale items for experts to review to ensure the validity and relevance of the content.

5. Assessment of the Inclusion of Validation Items: Check if the scale includes items that help validate the accuracy of the measurements, ensuring that the scale robustly reflects the concept of interest.

6. Application of Pretest: Conduct a pretest with a representative sample to identify potential problems and assess the understanding of the items.

7. Assessing Individual Item Performance: Analyze the performance of each item on the scale to determine its effectiveness in measuring the concept and adjust as necessary.

8. Scale Optimization: Refine and optimize the scale based on internal consistency indices to confirm its accuracy and effectiveness in measuring the concept.

This systematic approach ensures that measurement scales are rigorously developed and validated, increasing the quality and reliability of research using these tools.

Table 7 – Comparative evaluation of scales, according to DeVellis’ guide (2017).

Reference	Clarity	Item generation	Format	Revision	Inclusion of items	Pretest	Evaluation	Optimization
Al-Adwan et al. (2023)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Alami and El Idrissi (2022)	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	Yes	X	Yes	Yes
Cabada et al. (2017)	Yes	X	Yes	X	X	X	X	X
Ghai and Tandon (2023)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	Yes	Yes
Kashive et al. (2021)	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	Yes	X	Yes	Yes
Khan et al. (2024)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	X	Yes	Yes
Kumar and Tandon (2024)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Li and Yu (2020)	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	X	X	Yes	X
Maldonado et al. (2009)	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	X	Yes	Yes	X
Panigrahi et al. (2021)	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	X	Yes	Yes	X
Patil and Undale (2023)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	Yes	Yes
Salam and Farooq (2020)	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Vanitha and Alathur (2021)	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	X	Yes	Yes	Yes
Yuce et al. (2019)	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	X	Yes	Yes	X
Zhou et al. (2022)	Yes	Yes	Yes	X	X	X	Yes	Yes

Source: The authors.

Table 5 compares the measurement scales used in the reviewed articles with DeVellis's (2017) recommended steps. It shows that most studies did not fully adhere to these guidelines. Kumar and Tandon (2024) and Al-Adwan et al. (2023) are notable exceptions, having followed all proposed procedures. Initial steps like defining the measure, generating items, and choosing the measurement format were generally well handled. Clarity in construct definition and selection of measurement format were consistently met. All articles except Cabada et al. (2017) described item generation, with variations in the scoring systems used.

Significant gaps include the omission of expert reviews in five studies and the lack of pretesting in several articles, such as Cabada et al. (2017), Li and Yu (2020), and Kashive et al. (2021), which undermines content validation. While recent studies effectively evaluated items, earlier works like Cabada et al. (2017) and Maldonado et al. (2009) had flaws. Optimization was performed by Salam and Farooq (2020). Overall, initial steps were generally well-addressed, but later stages, including content validation and optimization, were inconsistently applied, impacting scale reliability and validity.

Table 8 presents data on sample characteristics, statistical analysis methods, and internal consistency indices. All analyzed articles, except for Cabada et al. (2017), utilized structural equation modeling (SEM). This approach indicates an exploratory nature of the studies, as SEM evaluates relationships among dimensions of a pre-defined model. It enables the examination of complex variable interactions and assesses how well the proposed model aligns with empirical data.

Table 8 – Methodology and sample selection

References	Technique	Cronbach's alpha range	Number of items	n	Participants
Al-Adwan et al. (2023)	PLS-SEM	0.85 – 0.92	26	574	Undergraduate students
Alami and El Idrissi (2022)	PLS-SEM	0.72 – 0.88	24	448	Undergraduate students (Business School)
Cabada et al. (2017)	Regression analysis	0.66 – 0.92	10	43	Undergraduate students (Engineer)
Ghai and Tandon (2023)	CB-SEM	0.85 – 0.92	31	382	Undergraduate students
Kashive et al. (2021)	PLS-SEM	0.80 – 0.89	27	100	Students and professionals using e-learning
Khan et al. (2024)	PLS-SEM	0.83 – 0.91	47	262	Information Technology administrators
Kumar and Tandon (2024)	CB-SEM	0.74 – 0.84	32	311	Undergraduate students
Li and Yu (2020)	CB-SEM	0.88 – 0.96	36	122	Undergraduate students
Maldonado et a. (2009)	PLS-SEM	> 0.7	21	150	Secondary school students
Panigrahi et al. (2021)	CB-SEM	0.82 – 0.93	43	412	Graduate students

Patil and Undale (2023)	CB-SEM	0.82 – 0.94	17	267	Undergraduate students
Salam and Farooq (2020)	PLS-SEM	0.85 – 0.94	48	80	Undergraduate students of service-learning
Vanitha and Alathur (2021)	PLS-SEM	0.70 – 0.91	66	704	Students and apprentices in India
Yuce et al. (2019)	CB-SEM	> 0.7	36	140	Students who used Intelligent tutoring systems
Zhou et al. (2022)	CB-SEM	0.70 – 0.94	25	301	Undergraduate students

Note: SEM: Structural Equation Modeling; PLS-SEM: Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling; CB-SEM: Covariance-based Structural Equation Modeling, n: sample size.

Source: Primary data, 2024.

Some studies, such as Kashive et al. (2021) and Cabada et al. (2017), used relatively small samples, which is noted as a limitation. However, these sample sizes were deemed sufficient for their research goals. Studies using structural equation modeling correctly performed factor analyses to ensure content validity and reliable scale performance. Factor analysis is crucial for retaining only appropriate items in a robust scale (DeVellis, 2017). All reviewed studies addressed internal reliability, using indices like Cronbach's Alpha to assess consistency over time and conditions. Validity and reliability are essential for a scale to accurately measure the intended construct and provide stable results. Despite some limitations in scale development, many studies adhered to recommended procedures for creating valid and reliable scales. Kumar and Tandon (2024) particularly exemplified rigorous, theoretically grounded, and statistically robust scale development. The thorough application of these procedures ensures effective measurement tools and high-quality research data.

4.3 Cross-Analysis Of Bibliometric Data And The Narrative Review

For this final analysis, we compared some bibliometric data with parameters used in the narrative review. The objective is to verify whether there is any relationship between the quality of the development of measurement scales created and used to examine AI-enabled VLEs and the performance metrics of the publications.

In Table 8, we present a summary of the information for the cross-analysis of bibliometric data and the narrative review.

Table 8 – Summary of the cross-analysis of bibliometric data and the narrative review

Publication-related							Citation metric	Narrative Review	
Reference	Year of publication	Journal	Journal Metrics				Nr Citations	Scale Development analysis	
			Cite Score	Quartile Scopus	SJR	H-index		Number of items completed	Technique
Al-Adwan et al. (2023)	2023	Education and Information Technologies	10	96%	1301	76	198	8	PLS-SEM
Alami and El Idrissi (2022)	2022	Arab Gulf Journal of Scientific Research	1	27%	0,181	15	32	6	PLS-SEM
Cabada et al. (2017)	2017	Telematics and Informatics	17	99%	1827	106	110	2	Regression analysis
Ghai and Tandon (2023)	2023	Education and Information Technologies	10	96%	1301	76	36	7	CB-SEM
Kashive et al. (2021)	2021	The International Journal of Information and Learning Technology	6,1	87%	0,721	-	114	6	PLS-SEM
Khan et al. (2024)	2024	Education and Information Technologies	10	96%	1301	76	4	6	PLS-SEM
Kumar and Tandon (2024)	2024	Education and Information Technologies	10	96%	1301	76	4	8	CB-SEM
Li and Yu (2020)	2020	Journal of Data, Information and Management	-	-	-	-	35	4	CB-SEM
Maldonado et al. (2009)	2009	ICCT 2009 - 4th Int. Conf. on Comp. Sci and Conv. Inf. Tech	-	-	-	-	63	5	PLS-SEM
Panigrahi et al. (2021)	2021	Information Technology and People	8,2	91%	1244	76	102	5	CB-SEM
Patil and Undale (2023)	2023	Education and Information Technologies	10	96%	1301	76	11	7	CB-SEM
Salam and Farooq (2020)	2020	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education	19,3	99%	2578	61	147	7	PLS-SEM
Vanitha and Alathur (2021)	2021	Education and Information Technologies	10	96%	1301	76	30	6	PLS-SEM
Yuce et al. (2019)	2019	Online Information Review	6,9	89%	0,876	75	61	5	CB-SEM
Zhou et al. (2022)	2022	Education and Information Technologies	10	96%	1301	76	37	5	CB-SEM

Source: Primary data, 2024.

Although a more extensive study is needed to definitively link article quality with performance metrics, the data in Table 8 provide some preliminary insights. Generally, journals with high publication metrics tend to have more publications. The recent articles from 2024

have fewer citations, suggesting that their lower citation counts might be due to insufficient time for dissemination rather than research quality, as noted by Van Noorden et al. (2014). Conversely, older articles, such as those from conferences, and those published in journals with no metrics, like Li and Yu (2020), have accumulated more citations over time.

Trends also emerge in the relationship between scale development techniques and the number of completed items. For instance, Cabada et al. (2017), which used the simplest technique, completed the fewest items but still had a notable citation count, possibly due to the journal's high metrics. The article by Al-Adwan et al. (2023), which had the highest number of citations, completed all items in scale development and was published in a high-metrics journal, suggesting that thorough scale development might enhance a paper's impact. Similarly, Salam and Farooq (2020), with seven completed items published in a top journal, also demonstrated a significant impact. These observations suggest that the thoroughness of scale development and the quality of the publication venue can influence a paper's academic impact.

5. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to evaluate the use of measurement scales for assessing Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs) enhanced by Artificial Intelligence (AI), focusing on students' motivational factors and methodological aspects of the scales employed. The systematic review identified fifteen pertinent articles, highlighting significant gaps in the methodological rigor of many scales. While these studies addressed important aspects of student motivation and the effectiveness of VLEs, critical analysis reveals inconsistencies in applying methodological standards, affecting the reliability of their findings.

Particularly, studies such as those by Alami and El Idrissi (2022), Zhou et al. (2022), and Li and Yu (2020) exhibited methodological shortcomings, including inadequate peer review and validation processes. Conversely, Kumar and Tandon (2024) and Al-Adwan et al. (2023) exemplified rigorous adherence to recommended procedures, ensuring robust scale development. The observed lack of methodological rigor in some articles underscores the need for future research to follow established steps in scale development meticulously. It is recommended that future studies explore emerging areas in AI and adapt scales to diverse educational contexts and learning styles. A rigorous methodology is essential for ensuring the accuracy and validity of measurements, thereby enhancing the quality of research and the effectiveness of VLEs in modern education.

REFERENCES

- AL-ADWAN, A. S.; LI, N.; AL-ADWAN, A.; ABBASI, G. A.; ALBELBISI, N. A.; HABIBI, A. Extending the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to predict university students' intentions to use metaverse-based learning platforms. **Education and Information Technologies**, v. 28, n. 11, p. 15381–15413, 2023. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11816-3>.
- ALAMI, Y.; EL IDRISSE, I. Students' adoption of e-learning: Evidence from a Moroccan business school in the COVID-19 era. **Arab Gulf Journal of Scientific Research**, v. 40, n. 1, p. 54–78, 2022. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1108/AGJSR-05-2022-0052>.
- ARGUEDAS, M.; XHAFA, F.; CASILLAS, L.; DARADOUMIS, T.; PEÑA, A.; CABALLÉ, S. A model for providing emotion awareness and feedback using fuzzy logic in online learning. **Soft Computing**, v. 22, n. 3, p. 963–977, 2016. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-016-2399-0>.
- BERTONCINI, A. L. C.; SERAFIM, M. C.; BORBA, E. H. D. Escalas de mensuração e antecedentes motivacionais de ambientes virtuais de aprendizado fomentados pela inteligência artificial. **Revista Tecnologias Educacionais em Rede (ReTER)**, 2023. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.5902/2675995070381>.
- CABADA, R. Z.; ESTRADA, M. L. B.; HERNÁNDEZ, F. G.; BUSTILLOS, R. O.; REYES-GARCÍA, C. A. An affective and Web 3.0-based learning environment for a programming language. **Telematics and Informatics**, v. 35, n. 3, p. 611–628, 2017. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2017.03.005>.
- CHEUNG, S. K. S.; KWOK, L. F.; PHUSAVAT, K.; YANG, H. H. Shaping the future learning environments with smart elements: Challenges and opportunities. **International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education**, v. 18, n. 1, p. 16, 2021. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-021-00254-1>.
- CHIU, C.; CHIU, C.; CHANG, H. Examining the integrated influence of fairness and quality on learners' satisfaction and Web-based learning continuance intention. **Information Systems Journal**, v. 17, n. 3, p. 271–287, 2007. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2575.2007.00238.x>.
- DAVIS, F. D. Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. **MIS Quarterly**, v. 13, n. 3, p. 319, 1989. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>.
- DJEKI, E.; DÉGILA, J.; BONDIONBOUY, C.; ALHASSAN, M. H. E-learning bibliometric analysis from 2015 to 2020. **Journal of Computers in Education**, v. 9, n. 4, p. 727–754, 2022. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-021-00218-4>.
- DELONE, W. H.; MCLEAN, E. R. Information systems success: The quest for the dependent variable. **Information Systems Research**, v. 3, n. 1, p. 60–95, 1992.
- DELONE, W. H.; MCLEAN, E. R. The DeLone and McLean model of information systems success: A ten-year update. **Journal of Management Information Systems**, v. 19, n. 4, p. 9–30, 2003.
- DEVELLIS, R. F. **Scale development: Theory and applications**. 4. ed. SAGE, 2017.
- DONTHU, N.; KUMAR, S.; MUKHERJEE, D.; PANDEY, N.; LIM, W. M. How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines. **Journal of Business Research**, v. 133, p. 285–296, 2021. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.070>.
- GHAI, A.; TANDON, U. Integrating gamification and instructional design to enhance usability of online learning. **Education and Information Technologies**, v. 28, n. 2, p. 2187–2206, 2023. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11202-5>.
- HEW, K. F.; JIA, C.; GONDA, D. E.; BAI, S. Transitioning to the “new normal” of learning in unpredictable times: Pedagogical practices and learning performance in fully online flipped classrooms. **International Journal**

of **Educational Technology in Higher Education**, v. 17, n. 1, p. 57, 2020. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-020-00234-x>.

JALAL, A.; MAHMOOD, M. Students' behavior mining in e-learning environment using cognitive processes with information technologies. **Education and Information Technologies**, v. 24, n. 5, p. 2797–2821, 2019. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-019-09892-5>.

JUSOH, S.; ALMAJALI, S.; ABUALBASAL, A. A study of user experience for e-learning using interactive online technologies. **Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology**, v. 97, n. 15, 2019.

KASHIVE, N.; POWALE, L.; KASHIVE, K. Understanding user perception toward artificial intelligence (AI) enabled e-learning. **The International Journal of Information and Learning Technology**, v. 38, n. 1, p. 1–19, 2021. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJILT-05-2020-0090>.

KHAN, W.; SOHAIL, S.; ROOMI, M. A.; NISAR, Q. A.; RAFAQ, M. Opening a new horizon in digitalization for e-learning in Malaysia: Empirical evidence of Covid-19. **Education and Information Technologies**, v. 29, n. 8, p. 9387–9416, 2024. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12176-8>.

KUMAR, P.; TANDON, U. Values enhanced technology adoption (VETA) concerning online learning in higher education institutions: Academician's perspective in India. **Education and Information Technologies**, v. 29, n. 10, p. 13025–13047, 2024. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12366-4>.

LI, H.; YU, J. Learners' continuance participation intention of collaborative group project in virtual learning environment: An extended TAM perspective. **Journal of Data, Information and Management**, v. 2, n. 1, p. 39–53, 2020. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42488-019-00017-8>.

MALDONADO, U. P. T.; KHAN, G. F.; MOON, J.; RHO, J. J. E-learning motivation, students' acceptance/use of educational portal in developing countries: A case study of Peru. In: ICCIT 2009 - 4th International Conference on Computer Sciences and Convergence Information Technology, 2009, p. 1431–1441. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCIT.2009.77>.

MONTIGO, L.; LAO, D. M. E-learning for introductory computer science concept on recursion applying two types of feedback methods in the learning assessment. **Asian Association of Open Universities Journal**, v. 12, n. 2, p. 218–229, 2017. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1108/AAOUJ-02-2017-0019>.

MORALES-SALAS, R. E.; INFANTE-MORO, J. C.; GALLARDO-PÉREZ, J. Evaluación de ambientes virtuales de aprendizaje. Una gestión para mejorar. **IJERI: International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation**, v. 13, p. 126–142, 2020. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.46661/ijeri.4593>.

OWENS, B. China seeks to showcase research clout by building its own publishing realm. **Nature**, v. 630, 2024.

PAGE, M. J.; MCKENZIE, J. E.; BOSSUYT, P. M.; BOUTRON, I.; HOFFMANN, T. C.; MULROW, C. D.; SHAMSEER, L.; TETZLAFF, J. M.; AKL, E. A.; BRENNAN, S. E.; CHOU, R.; GLANVILLE, J.; GRIMSHAW, J. M.; HRÓBJARTSSON, A.; LALU, M. M.; LI, T.; LODER, E. W.; MAYO-WILSON, E.; MCDONALD, S.; ... MOHER, D. The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. **BMJ**, n. 71, 2021. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.

PANIGRAHI, R.; SRIVASTAVA, P. R.; PANIGRAHI, P. K. Effectiveness of e-learning: The mediating role of student engagement on perceived learning effectiveness. **Information Technology and People**, v. 34, n. 7, 2021. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITP-07-2019-0380>.

PATIL, H.; UNDALE, S. Willingness of university students to continue using e-learning platforms after compelled adoption of technology: Test of an extended UTAUT model. **Education and Information Technologies**, v. 28, n. 11, p. 14943–14965, 2023. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11778-6>.

RAMOS-RODRÍGUEZ, A.; RUÍZ-NAVARRO, J. Changes in the intellectual structure of strategic management research: A bibliometric study of the **Strategic Management Journal**, 1980–2000. **Strategic Management Journal**, v. 25, n. 10, p. 981–1004, 2004. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.397>.

ROBLEK, V.; MESHKO, M.; DIMOVSKI, V.; PETERLIN, J. Smart technologies as social innovation and complex social issues of the Z generation. **Kybernetes**, v. 48, n. 1, p. 91–107, 2018. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1108/K-09-2017-0356>.

SALAM, M.; FAROOQ, M. S. Does sociability quality of web-based collaborative learning information system influence students' satisfaction and system usage? **International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education**, v. 17, n. 1, 2020. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-020-00189-z>.

SAYAF, A. M. Adoption of e-learning systems: An integration of ISSM and constructivism theories in higher education. **Heliyon**, v. 9, e13014, 2023. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e13014>.

SNYDER, H. Literature review as a research methodology: An overview and guidelines. **Journal of Business Research**, v. 104, p. 333–339, 2019. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.07.039>.

VAN NOORDEN, R.; MAHER, B.; NUZZO, R. The top 100 papers. **Nature**, v. 514, 2014.

VANITHA, P. S.; ALATHUR, S. Factors influencing e-learning adoption in India: Learners' perspective. **Education and Information Technologies**, v. 26, n. 5, p. 5199–5236, 2021. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10504-4>.

VENKATESH, V.; MORRIS, M. G.; DAVIS, G. B.; DAVIS, F. D. User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. **MIS Quarterly**, v. 27, n. 3, p. 425–478, 2003. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.2307/30036540>.

VODENKO, K. V.; LYAU-SHEVA, S. A. Science and education in the form 4.0: Public policy and organization based on human and artificial intellectual capital. **Journal of Intellectual Capital**, v. 21, n. 4, p. 549–564, 2020. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIC-11-2019-0274>.

WALTMAN, L. A review of the literature on citation impact indicators. **Journal of Informetrics**, v. 10, n. 2, p. 365–391, 2016. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2016.02.007>.

YUCE, A.; ABUBAKAR, A. M.; ILKAN, M. Intelligent tutoring systems and learning performance: Applying task-technology fit and IS success model. **Online Information Review**, v. 43, n. 4, p. 600–616, 2019. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-11-2017-0340>.

ZHOU, M.; DZINGIRAI, C.; HOVE, K.; CHITATA, T.; MUGANDANI, R. Adoption, use and enhancement of virtual learning during COVID-19. **Education and Information Technologies**, v. 27, p. 8939–8959, 2022. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-10985-x>.